

Large-scale Mapping and Classification of Agricultural Terraces in the European Mediterranean

Andrei Kedich ^{a,b}, Ralf Vandam ^b, Soetkin Vervust ^b, Yannick Devos ^b, Matthias Vanmaercke ^a

^a Division of Geography and Tourism, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, KU Leuven, Heverlee, Belgium — andrei.kedich@kuleuven.be; matthias.vanmaercke@kuleuven.be

^b Archaeology, Environmental Changes & Geo-Chemistry research group (AMGC), Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels, Belgium — ralf.vandam@vub.be; soetkin.vervust@vub.be; yannick.devos@vub.be

Abstract

Agricultural terraces are among the most significant anthropogenic landscape modifications in the European Mediterranean, yet consistent large-scale data on their distribution and typology remain scarce. This study presents the first continental-scale terrace classification map at 10 m resolution, spanning from Portugal to Turkey, explicitly distinguishing between traditional and industrial terrace types. A multimodal U-Net++ deep learning framework integrates Sentinel-1 SAR, Sentinel-2 imagery, terrain derivatives, and land cover data. Trained on 868 manually annotated tiles covering 13,250 ha of terraces, the model demonstrates promising preliminary performance.

Keywords: agricultural terraces, remote sensing, deep learning

1. Introduction

Agricultural terraces¹ are among the most prominent anthropogenic landscape modifications in the European Mediterranean (Tarolli et al., 2014). They convert steep and marginal terrain into arable land by reducing slope gradients, increasing effective soil depth, and facilitating cultivation and irrigation. Beyond their agricultural function, terraces play an important role in regulating hydrological and geomorphological processes by reducing runoff velocity, enhancing infiltration, and limiting soil erosion. As such, they represent a key land-management strategy in mountainous and hilly environments.

Despite their importance, terrace systems across the Mediterranean are increasingly affected by contrasting land-use pressures. In many remote areas, agricultural abandonment has accelerated

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Poster Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

due to rural depopulation, changing market conditions, and reforms of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (Renwick et al., 2013; Ustaoglu & Collier, 2018). As maintenance declines, formerly stable terrace systems deteriorate, leading to wall collapse, gully erosion, piping, and in some cases landslides (Tarolli et al., 2014; Arnáez et al., 2015; Lesschen et al., 2008). Conversely, in more intensively cultivated regions, rising demand for crops such as olives and grapes has driven the construction of new terraces. These modern terraces typically have wider benches, steeper risers, and lack traditional stone reinforcement, making them structurally different from historic systems and often more susceptible to erosion and mass movement (Cots-Folch et al., 2006). As a result, terraces can both reduce and intensify erosion depending on their design, condition, and management.

Although many local studies have examined terrace morphology and geomorphic effects, large-scale assessments remain limited (Tarolli et al., 2014; Arnáez et al., 2015; Lesschen et al., 2008; Moreno-de-las-Heras et al., 2019). This is mainly due to the lack of consistent, high-resolution spatial data on terrace distribution and typology. Existing large-scale mapping efforts have mostly focused on detecting terraces as a single class, often relying on very high-resolution remote sensing or LiDAR data (Diaz-Varela et al., 2014; Paliaga et al., 2020), which limits their applicability over large areas. While recent studies have demonstrated the feasibility of terrace detection using medium-resolution data at continental or global scales, these approaches do not distinguish between different terrace types and primarily focus on modern terraces within cropland areas in Asia (Li et al., 2025; Lu et al., 2023).

This study addresses these limitations by developing an automated deep learning framework for large-scale mapping of agricultural terraces across the European Mediterranean. To our knowledge, this represents the first attempt to produce a spatially continuous terrace map at 10 m resolution for this region, while explicitly differentiating between terrace types. Unlike previous large-scale approaches that either treat terraces as a single undifferentiated class or focus primarily on Asian croplands, this framework distinguishes between two morphologically and functionally distinct categories. Traditional terraces are typically narrow and supported by stone walls, whereas industrial or modern terraces are characterized by wider benches of up to 30–40 m and mechanically constructed risers reaching 5–7 m in height (Cots-Folch et al., 2006; Londrero et al., 2018) (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Examples of annotated terraced systems: (a) traditional terraces reinforced with stone walls, and (b) industrial terraces constructed using heavy machinery (Source: Google Earth Pro).

2. Methodology

The classification framework integrates Sentinel-1 SAR, Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, the Copernicus DEM GLO-30 (ESA, 2022), and the ESA WorldCover 2021 land-cover dataset (Zanaga et al., 2022), all at or resampled to a uniform 10 m spatial resolution. In total, 16 input bands were selected from an initial pool of 28 through feature selection based on correlation analysis, Cliff's Delta effect size, and Random Forest importance, applied on a sample of pixels from manually annotated traditional and industrial terrace polygons. The final band stack combines Sentinel-1 SAR backscatter (VV and VH polarization for spring and summer), Sentinel-2 reflectance, NDVI, and EVI aggregated as seasonal medians, slope and elevation derived from the Copernicus DEM GLO-30, and the WorldCover land-cover classification.

The study area was divided into 256×256 -pixel tiles of 2.56×2.56 km. Training data were collected across 868 tiles (5,688 km²), covering approximately 13,250 ha of mapped terraces, of which 5,620 ha are traditional and 7,630 ha industrial. Within the industrial category, 2,540 ha correspond to a reforestation/erosion-control subcategory. Annotation consistency is assessed through independent re-labeling of five percent of the samples.

The dataset is split into training, validation, and test sets at the patch level following a 70/15/15 ratio, minimizing spatial autocorrelation and ensuring robust model evaluation. Classification is performed using a U-Net++ convolutional neural network in a multimodal configuration, combining spectral, backscatter, topographic, and land-cover inputs to predict two terrace classes: traditional and industrial.

3. Results

Feature selection identified SAR backscatter bands as the most discriminative features for separating traditional and industrial terraces, with Sentinel-1 VH backscatter median composites for both spring and summer showing the largest Cliff's Delta effect sizes. Summer Sentinel-2 bands

and composites, including SWIR, NDVI, and Green, also demonstrated medium to large effect sizes. Random Forest importance rankings also confirmed Sentinel-1 VH spring and summer backscatter as among the most important predictors, alongside elevation and the Sentinel-2 red-edge band. Together, these findings highlight the complementary role of SAR backscatter, optical seasonal contrasts, and terrain elevation in discriminating between terrace types.

Preliminary classification results of overall terrace detection yield a Receiver Operating Characteristic Area Under the Curve (ROC AUC) of approximately 0.83, with F1 scores of 0.76 for both classes.

4. Conclusion

This study presents the first continental-scale classification of agricultural terraces across the European Mediterranean at 10 m resolution, explicitly distinguishing between traditional and industrial terrace types. Feature selection analysis demonstrated that SAR backscatter and optical seasonal contrasts are highly informative for terrace type discrimination. Initial classification results indicate that the framework can successfully detect and differentiate terrace types across diverse Mediterranean landscapes, though the presented framework should be regarded as a proof of concept demonstrating the potential of automated large-scale terrace mapping using freely available data. Further methodological refinement and expanded training data collection will follow. The resulting classification map is intended to support large-scale assessments of land degradation, soil erosion, hydrological and geomorphological processes, and long-term agricultural land-use change across the Mediterranean.

References

- Arnáez J, Lana-Renault N, Lasanta T et al (2015) Effects of farming terraces on hydrological and geomorphological processes. A review. *CATENA* 128:122–134
- Cots-Folch R, Martínez-Casasnovas JA, Ramos MC (2006) Land terracing for new vineyard plantations in the north-eastern Spanish Mediterranean region: Landscape effects of the EU Council Regulation policy for vineyards' restructuring. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 115:88–96
- Diaz-Varela RA, Zarco-Tejada PJ, Angileri V et al (2014) Automatic identification of agricultural terraces through object-oriented analysis of very high resolution DSMs and multispectral imagery obtained from an unmanned aerial vehicle. *J Environ Manage* 134:117–126
- European Space Agency (ESA) (2022) Copernicus Digital Elevation Model GLO-30. Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
- Lesschen JP, Cammeraat LH, Nieman T (2008) Erosion and terrace failure due to agricultural land abandonment in a semi-arid environment. *Earth Surf Process Landf* 33:1574–1584
- Li Y, Tian F, Zhang M et al (2025) A 10-meter global terrace mapping using sentinel-2 imagery and topographic features with deep learning methods and cloud computing platform support. *Int J Appl Earth Obs Geoinformation* 139:104528

- Londero AL, Minella JPG, Deuschle D et al (2018) Impact of broad-based terraces on water and sediment losses in no-till (paired zero-order) catchments in southern Brazil. *J Soils Sediments* 18:1159–1175
- Lu Y, Li X, Xin L et al (2023) Mapping the terraces on the Loess Plateau based on a deep learning-based model at 1.89 m resolution. *Sci Data* 10:115
- Moreno-de-las-Heras M, Lindenberger F, Latron J et al (2019) Hydro-geomorphological consequences of the abandonment of agricultural terraces in the Mediterranean region: Key controlling factors and landscape stability patterns. *Geomorphology* 333:73–91
- Paliaga G, Luino F, Turconi L et al (2020) Terraced landscapes on Portofino Promontory (Italy): Identification, geo-hydrological hazard and management. *Water* 12:435
- Renwick A, Jansson T, Verburg PH et al (2013) Policy reform and agricultural land abandonment in the EU. *Land Use Policy* 30:446–457
- Tarolli P, Preti F, Romano N (2014) Terraced landscapes: From an old best practice to a potential hazard for soil degradation due to land abandonment. *Anthropocene* 6:10–25
- Ustaoglu E, Collier MJ (2018) Farmland abandonment in Europe: an overview of drivers, consequences, and assessment of the sustainability implications. *Environ Rev* 26:396–416
- Zanaga D, Van De Kerchove R, Daems D et al (2022) ESA WorldCover 10 m 2021 v200. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7254221>